

IMPACT OF ADMISSION PROCESS ON TEACHER TRAINING COURSE

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Abstract –

This paper purports to investigate the admission process and academic planning of the teacher training institution. The admission process is very important of professional education of teachers is essential for the qualitative improvement of education. The degree result of the various universities is not declared within time. After declaration of result students fill up the option form with details of mark and subject. The academic planning done at the college level when all candidates were admitted in the college. This research paper examines the terms accountability and effectiveness by how centralized admission process completed within a time.

Keywords – Admission Process, Teacher Training, Academic calendar,
Students – teacher.

Introduction –

One of the important features of educational development in the post- independence period was the rapid expansion of professional education. The teacher Training institution major focus is to produce effective ideal teachers who can guide future generations of the nation according to the society. At the same time there has been a rapid expansion in arts, commerce and science courses at the first degree level and this has been dictated not so much by the enrollment capacity of the institutions concerned or the employment opportunities available but by the pressures of public demand which have increased immensely on account of the reasons. The effect of this expansion on standards has been even more adverse. Teacher training Institution inspire Students teacher transfer on knowledge, skills and values to prepare young people to become successful learners, confident individuals and responsible citizens who can make a positive contribution to society. The admission process holds out an opportunity to expand the access to quality education and

improve the training education. Teacher training institution prepare an authentic academic calendar that reflects the philosophy and goals of the teacher training institution. It should include inclusive education, learner centered pedagogy and self-directed learning.

Objectives of the Study:-

1. To study the various part of admission process.
2. To study the admission process and academic calendar correlation.

Research Methodology:-

The research paper was a descriptive field research with the aim to explore the relation between the admission process impacts on academic calendar and draw conclusion relating to them.

Sample:-

Teacher training colleges involved in centralized admission process in 2011-12

Total No. of College Involved in Centralized admission Process (2011-12)	Status	Total No of Associates and Assistant professors.	Total No. of trainee students admitted in the college
23	Govt.,Aided and non-aided	158	2100

The research paper population comprised 23 teacher training colleges involved in Centralized admission Process (2011-12). A total number of 130 questionnaires were completed from a total no. of Associates and Assistant professors i.e.82.28% who had been working in the teacher training college.800 questionnaires was completed from trainee students who admitted in the teacher training institution in the academic year 2011-2012. The pupil’s teacher prescription of eligibility by the universities and pupils teacher selects the option of teacher training institution in the admission process.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA:-

The study explores the difference in the perception of the role of practical activity and admission process according to admission process round.

Cours ePape randS ection	TitleName of Paperand section	Marks	Hours	%Complete d within time	%Adjustment
I	Education in Emerging Indian Society.Section-I. Philosophical foundations ofEducation Section.II.Sociological foundations ofEducation.	100	100	35	78
II	Development of Learner & Teachinglearning process.Section-I. Development of Learner. Section-II. Psychology of Learning &Teaching.	100	100	30	65
III	Secondary and Higher SecondaryEducation.- History, Issues and school management.Section-I Secondary & Higher SecondaryEducation- History and Issues. Section-II. School Management.	100	100	50	50
IV	Essential of Educational Technology andInformation	100	100	45	88

	Technology. Section-I. Essential of Educational Technology. Section-II. Information Technology.				
V	Trends in Education and Electives. Section-I. Trends in Education. Section-II. Electives.	100	100	55	75
VI	Specialisation in methodology of any two School Subjects. Section-I. First Method. Section-II. Second Method.	100	100	40	85
Practical	Micro-Teaching	30	84	65	95
2	Class room Teaching	110	214	20	90
3	Simulation Teaching	10	10	65	50
4	Content-Cum. Methodology	20	30	50	75
5	Models of Teaching	20	22	45	85
6	Information Technology	10	6	35	70
7	Socially Useful productive work	20	10	40	60
8	Physical and Health education	20	10	25	80
9	Creativity and personality Development Programme.	20	10	60	70
10	Educational Aids	20	10	50	50

11	Practical related to theory papers	60	40	100	100
12	Assignment (Per paper-2)	20	30	100	100
13	Internal Examination	20	30	35	80
14	Internship	50	72	50	90
15	Action Research	50	22	40	75
16	Practice teaching Exam.Two lessonsOral examination	100	50	40	80

1. The admission is depend upon the undergraduate stage in arts, commerce and science courses. In 2011-2012 the enrollment of girls at teacher training course level shows considerable improvement.
2. The above table shows that the percentage of adjustment for course is greater than the regular objectives. The six theory papers, teaching methodology, and specialization paper, Practice teaching, practical activities were not as per module of course.
3. All the working group in the teacher training institution agreed such adjustment in course.
4. The pupil's teacher does not provide a better an environment gives the pupils a place of importance, a feeling of higher self-esteem, freedom to explore and experiment and opportunities to desire pleasure and satisfaction through joyful interactions.
5. The admission process affects the integrated parts of the entire process of teacher training.
6. Majority of the pupils are interested to take admission on teacher training course available as per the option.

Conclusion:

The result shows that greater percentage of the teacher educator had speedily completed the practical. All teacher educators had implanted the order of heads of the teacher training institution. The admission process indirectly stresses the need to train teachers. Though all the teacher educators had sensitivity towards teacher training course, none of them had satisfaction about training course. It indicate that admission process play a significant role in teacher training course.

Suggestions:-

1. Prepare a admission process model from June to onwards and time Management must be followed it is essential for training.
2. Planned an academic calendar for excellence teacher educators must be able to attract and identify, motivate, enthuse and inspire the pupils teacher.
3. Teacher training course is helpful for future teacher profession and they give deeper knowledge of teaching methodology. So admission process is introduced at graduate level throughout the state.
4. Preparation of proper annual planning provide to pupils teacher are important.

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